

U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service

ECOS

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Olive ridley sea turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*)

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Taxonomy: [View taxonomy in ITIS](#)

Listing Status: Endangered and Threatened

The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS) and the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) are joint lead Federal agencies responsible for managing this species; in general, the FWS manages species in inland waters and on land, while NMFS manages species in marine waters. The information on this page displays mostly FWS data; for additional information on this species, including NMFS regulatory actions such as critical habitat designation or recovery planning, please visit the National Marine Fisheries website (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/species-directory/threatened-endangered>).

General Information

The olive ridley was named for the olive color of its heart-shaped shell and is one of the smallest of the sea turtles, with adults reaching 2 to 2.5 feet in length and weighing 80 to 110 pounds. The species may be identified by the uniquely high and variable numbers of vertebral and costal scutes. Although some individuals have only five pairs of costals, in nearly all cases some division of costal scutes occurs, so that as many as six to nine pairs may be present. In addition, the vertebral scutes also show frequent division, as do the scales on the dorsal surface of the head. The prefrontal scales, however, typically number two pairs. Existing reports suggest that the olive ridley's diet includes crabs, shrimp, rock lobsters, jellyfish, and tunicates. In some parts of the world, algae has been reported as its principal food.

Population detail

The following populations are being monitored: Olive ridley sea turtle

Current Listing Status Summary

Show entries

Status	Date Listed	Lead Region	Where Listed
Threatened	07-28-1978	Pacific Region (Region 1)	Wherever found, except when listed as endangered un
Endangered	07-28-1978	Washington Office	Breeding colony populations on Pacific coast of Mexico.

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» Range Information

Current Range

Last Updated: 09-04-2025 - *Wherever found, except when listed as endangered under 50 CFR 224.101*

Zoom in! Some species' locations may be small and hard to see from a wide perspective. To narrow-in on locations, check the state and county lists (below) and then use the zoom tool.

Want the FWS's current range for all species? Click [here](#) to download a zip file containing all individual shapefiles and metadata for all species.

* For consultation needs do not use only this current range map, please use [IPaC](#).

Current range maps are only shown within the jurisdictional boundaries of the United States of America. The species may also occur outside this region.

- **Breeding colony populations on Pacific coast of Mexico**

Listing status: Endangered

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur:
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur:
- **Countries** in which this population is known to occur: Mexico

- **Wherever found, except when listed as endangered under 50 CFR 224.101**

Listing status: Threatened

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: Hawaii
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur: Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument
- **Countries** in which this population is known to occur: Angola, Antigua and Barbuda, Australia, Bangladesh, Benin, Brazil, Brunei, Cambodia, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Chile, Colombia, Congo, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Federated States of Micronesia, French Guiana, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guadeloupe, Guatemala, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Guyana, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Iran, Ivory Coast, Jamaica, Japan, Kenya, Liberia, Madagascar, Malaysia, Maldives, Martinique, Mauritania, Mexico, Morocco, Mozambique, Myanmar (Burma), Namibia, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Oman, Pakistan, Panama, Papua New Guinea, Peru, Philippines, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Sudan, Suriname, Taiwan, Tanzania, Thailand, Togo, Trinidad and Tobago, United States, Venezuela, Vietnam, Yemen

» Candidate Information

No Candidate information available for this species.

No Candidate Assessments available for this species.

No Candidate Notice of Review Documents currently available for this species.

No Uplisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Federal Register Documents

Federal Register Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Su Dc
07/23/2014	79 FR 42687 42696	Marine and Anadromous Taxa: Additions, Removal, Updates, and Corrections to the List of Endangered and Threatened Wildlife	
10/10/2012	77 FR 61573 61574	Initiation of 5-Year Review for Kemp's Ridley, Olive Ridley, Leatherback, and Hawksbill Sea Turtles	
04/21/2005	70 FR 20734 20736	Initiation of a 5-Year Review of Listed Sea Turtles	
03/23/1999	64 FR 14052 14077	(NOAA/NMFS) Endangered and Threatened Species; Regulations Consolidation; Final Rule	
06/29/1987	52 FR 24244 24262	NOAA--Sea Turtle Conservation; Shrimp Trawling Requirements; 52 FR 24244- 24262	
05/01/1980	45 FR 29054 29055	Threatened Fish and Wildlife; Green, Loggerhead, and Olive Ridley Sea Turtles	
03/19/1980	45 FR 17588 17589	ETWP; Green, Loggerhead, and Olive Ridley Sea Turtles	
07/28/1978	43 FR 32800	Listing and Protecting Loggerhead Sea Turtles as "Threatened Species" and Populations	

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» Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

No Species Status Assessments (SSA's) are currently available for this species.

Special Rule Publications

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title
06/29/1987	52 FR 24244 24262	NOAA--Sea Turtle Conservation; Shrimp Trawling Requirements; 52 FR 24244- 24262
07/28/1978	43 FR 32800 32811	Listing and Protecting Loggerhead Sea Turtles as "Threatened Species" and Populations

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» Recovery

- [Species with Recovery Documents Data Explorer](#)
- Recovery Priority Number: 8C

Current Recovery Plan(s)

Show entries

Date	Plan Stage	Recovery Plan	Implementation Status	SSAs/Biological Reports	Recovery Impleme Strategies
01/12/1998	Final Revision 1	Recovery Plan for U.S. Pacific Populations of the Olive Ridley Turtle	View Implementation Progress		

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Other Recovery Documents

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions and notices as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions and notices.

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Document Type
10/10/2012	77 FR 61573 61574	Initiation of 5-Year Review for Kemp's Ridley, Olive Ridley, Leatherback, and Hawksbill Sea Turtles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five Year Review Information S
04/21/2005	70 FR 20734 20736	Initiation of a 5-Year Review of Listed Sea Turtles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five Year Review Information S

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Five Year Reviews

Note: This report includes actual Five Year Review completions as well as records that act as Five Year Review completions.

Show entries

Date	Title
06/18/2014	Olive ridley sea turtle(Lepidochelys olivacea) 5-Year Review
08/21/2007	Olive ridley sea turtle(Lepidochelys olivacea) 5-Year Review
08/21/2007	Olive ridley sea turtle(Lepidochelys olivacea) 5-Year Review

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No Delisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Critical Habitat

No Critical Habitat Documents currently available for this species.

» Conservation Plans

No Conservation Plans currently available for this species.

» Petitions

No Petitions currently available for this species.

» Biological Opinions

To see all FWS Issued Biological Opinions please visit the [BO Report](#).

» Life History

No Life History information has been entered into this system for this species.

» Other Resources

[NatureServe Explorer Species Reports](#)-- NatureServe Explorer is a source for authoritative conservation information on more than 50,000 plants, animals and ecological communities of the U.S and Canada. NatureServe Explorer provides in-depth information on rare and endangered species, but includes common plants and animals too. NatureServe Explorer is a product of NatureServe in collaboration with the Natural Heritage Network.

[ITIS Reports](#)-- ITIS (the Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a source for authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world.

[FWS Digital Media Library](#) -- The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Digital Library is a searchable collection of selected images, historical artifacts, audio clips, publications, and video." +